

EXAMINATION OF THE SURFACE MORPHOLOGY OF Ti6Al4V IN THE SURFACE ROUGHNESS FORMED ON DENTAL IMPLANTS BY THE SANDBLASTING METHOD

¹EBRU YABAS, ²MUSTAFA CETIN, ²VILDAN DEMIREZEN, ²KAMER ŞAHIN, ³MEHMET SIMSIR, ²FATİH OZAYDIN

¹Sivas Cumhuriyet University, Advanced Technology Application and Research Center, Sivas, Türkiye, eyabas@cumhuriyet.edu.tr

²ESTAŞ Eksantrik Sanayi ve Ticaret A.Ş., Sivas, Türkiye, mustafa.cetin@estas.com.tr

³Sivas Cumhuriyet University, Faculty of Engineering, Sivas, Türkiye, msimsir@cumhuriyet.edu.tr

Abstract

Ti6Al4V alloy is preferred in dental implants due to its properties such as high biocompatibility and osteogenesis, excellent strength, toughness, creep, corrosion resistance and low elastic modulus. It is known that surface properties are as important as surgical technique, implant material and implant design in ensuring osseointegration in dental implants. In this study, we created homogeneous surface roughness on the outer surfaces of dental implants produced by ESTAŞ by using the sandblasting method in order to increase their connection with bone and examined their surface properties with SEM. As a result of these investigations, we determined the optimum working conditions for the sandblasting and SLA methods to be used in production.

Keywords: Dental implant, Ti6Al4V, sandblasting, SLA, SEM.

1. INTRODUCTION

Dental implants, which are a common technique used today to overcome tooth loss, have a greatly positive impact on people's health. However, after applying dental implants, the biggest problem of dentists is the separation of the implant from the bone and the resulting infection. Separation of the implant from the bone is based on the result that the interaction between the living tissue and the implant is not sufficient. Creating an interface compatible with bone tissue also increases the healing rate, and more comprehensive studies on this subject are needed [1-3]. Examining the surface properties of the implant has an important place in ensuring osseointegration, which is defined as a direct structural and functional connection between living bone tissue and the implant surface under loading, without fibrous tissue. Because the response of bone tissue varies depending on the surface properties of the implant [4-9]. The surface roughening process of titanium implants with sandblasting technique is a technique that first started in 1986 and continues to be implemented. Sandblasted Large Grid Acid-Etched (SLA), on the other hand, is based on creating macro roughness by spraying large sand grains onto the implant while creating implant surfaces. Since SLA gives the implant surface a hydrophilic feature, it provides adhesion thanks to micropores when placed into the tissue [4-6, 10-12]. When the studies in the literature are examined, it is seen that implant surface properties play a role on the healing response of the bone, and among the surface preparation methods, morphological methods have more pronounced effects than physical and chemical methods. Rough surfaces provide a positive response, and among the methods used to obtain a rough surface, sandblasting appears to give successful results.

Therefore, in this study, we created surface roughness on the implant by applying sandblasting and SLA techniques under different conditions in order to increase the interaction between the implant and the bone surface. Then, we examined the surface roughness with a scanning electron microscope (SEM) and determined the optimum conditions of surface roughness generation techniques.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PART

The dental implants used in this study are implants produced by ESTAŞ and are made of Ti6Al4V ELI (ASTM F136 Grade 23) material, and Grade 23 was used to increase biocompatibility. The surface morphologies of the implants, whose surface roughness was created by sandblasting and SLA methods, were examined with TESCAN MIRA 3 XMU SEM.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, we examined the surface properties of dental implants by creating surface roughness under different conditions with the sandblasting method. Sandblasting processes were applied by changing the sand thickness, pressure and time parameters and the surface properties were examined. In order to reach the desired roughness level, studies continued with f60 (212-300 microns) Al₂O₃. After this study, the Ra value was found to be 3 and above. Then, to select the appropriate pressure, sandblasting was done with the same sand for 10 sec at 2 bar, 3 bar and 4 bar pressures. According to Ra and Rz values, it was decided that the appropriate pressure should be 3 bars. Then, SLA was applied to all 2-4 bar samples and Ra, Rz values and SEM images were examined. Sand was not observed in the SEM images. Observing sand after SLA is an outcome we do not want. Then, pressure, regulator difference and speed difference studies were carried out and surface properties were examined. According to SEM and EDX results, the optimum values are as in Table 1.

The obtained results are the values at which the desired surface properties can be created, and they were used as a trial to create the outer surface roughness of the implants produced by ESTAŞ.

Table 1 According to SEM and EDX results, the optimum values

Sample	Sand Particle Size	Washing Time	Sand Pressure	Temperature	Cycle	Time	Measurement value	Measurement value
							Ra	Rz
Implant After Sandblasting	212-300 Micron Al ₂ O ₃ White, Round	10 sec	3 bar	30°C	280 rpm	10 sec	3.42	21.28
Implant After SLA	212-300 Micron Al ₂ O ₃ White, Round	10 sec	3 bar	30°C	280 rpm	10 sec	2.81	18.46

As can be seen from the SEM images at different magnifications in Figures 1 and 2, it is seen that homogeneous rough surfaces of similar sizes are formed on the surfaces of the implants. We can conclude that the applied methods and determined optimum conditions are applicable in production.

Figure 1 SEM images after sandblasting in different magnifications

Figure 2 SEM images after SLA in different magnifications

4. CONCLUSION

Ti6Al4V alloy, which is preferred in implant systems, attracts attention due to its many properties as well as its biocompatibility. In this study, we used sandblasting and SLA methods to create roughness on the surfaces of implant systems produced using Ti6Al4V alloy. We examined the surface properties of these methods under similar conditions. We used SEM and EDX data of the prepared surfaces when determining the best optimum conditions. According to the results, we observed the best results at 30°C temperature, 280 rpm cycle for 10 sec, and 3 bar pressure. When the SEM images were examined, it was observed that a homogeneous surface was obtained.

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